

28 may partially be related to the way scientists position themselves. If scientists do not
29 convincingly communicate about the implications of their evidence, other interested
30 stakeholders will drive the conversations. To increase societal impact, scientists must
31 understand the complex communication environment and take an informed and strategic
32 position. We describe the prevailing conservation and farming narratives, highlighting how the
33 term biodiversity can be used to start dialogues between parties with conflicting demands, and
34 exemplify how scientists can build effective narratives.

35 Main Text:

36 **Effective communication about biodiversity-friendly farming is urgent.**

37 Humanity is facing the challenge of feeding an increasing population without causing
38 more environmental damage [1,2]. We need to speed up action as the consequences of habitat
39 loss and climate change are already threatening both biodiversity and food security [3,4].
40 Society –and policymakers– are therefore increasingly interested in transitioning towards more
41 sustainable food systems [5]. Despite considerable debate, most scientists agree that the
42 agricultural footprint on biodiversity, soil, water, and air needs to be reduced, while production
43 efficiency needs to be improved [6]. This implies halting the conversion of (semi-)natural
44 habitat to agriculture, diminishing agricultural dependency on external outputs, and reducing
45 food loss and waste, while accounting for aspects related to universal access to healthy diets
46 [7].

47 New strategic agendas are being deployed to mainstream biodiversity management
48 across sectors [8,9], specifically in agriculture [10]. Promoting biodiversity as a key element
49 in agriculture does not only have conservation purposes but is essential to guarantee nature's
50 contributions to people through the provision of ecosystem services such as pollination, soil
51 fertility, and pest control. However, despite the growing evidence highlighting the benefits of

52 integrating biodiversity management into farming practices [11,12], and international policy
53 efforts to promote this [13], the uptake of science-based **biodiversity-friendly farming** (see
54 Glossary) is slow at best [14,15]. This may, at least partially, be caused by the main research
55 focus and outreach strategies of the scientific community not always being aligned with
56 farmers' perceptions and needs [12,16], precluding an effective and engaging communication.

57 To promote practical and operational biodiversity-friendly farming, scientists inevitably
58 need to join forces with other stakeholders [17]. Scientists have often been criticised for hiding
59 away in ivory towers, disconnected from everyday life problems. For example, many papers
60 on biodiversity conservation on farmland end with vague statements without specifying how
61 those can translate to agricultural practices [18–20]. Fortunately, this is changing rapidly.
62 Worldwide, translational research for sustainability is gaining momentum [21–23], including
63 scientists as legitimate stakeholders with a clear voice in the societal debate. The demands on
64 scientists to communicate with non-scientists are growing. Especially ecologists and
65 agronomists working at the interface of farming and biodiversity conservation are spending a
66 rapidly increasing proportion of time communicating about their research to address desired
67 conservation or sustainable goals. However, the forces at play in communication with non-
68 scientist stakeholders are markedly different from the more formalized rules of scientific
69 communication but are the ones that can strongly influence the societal impact scientists have.

70 For optimal societal impact, scientific knowledge transfer should do more than just
71 enumerating evidence [24]. Changing human behavioural is extremely complex, as humans are
72 influenced by their social, material, economic, and cultural contexts [25]. Hence, impactful
73 results need to present evidence in tailored clear and inspiring messages. Unfortunately,
74 researchers are rarely trained to be effective communicators. **Effective communication** seeks
75 to connect with target audiences by considering their needs and understanding their relevant

76 contexts [26]. In the case of biodiversity-friendly farming there is a wide range of potential
77 audiences comprising amongst others, farmers, agribusiness, retailers, and consumers. These
78 audiences often require an engaging and strategic **narrative**.

79 Narratives are subjective and generally used to influence people in a desired way, but
80 can (and should) be based on objectively obtained scientific evidence. However, evidence can
81 always be framed to support the interests of the narrator. In fact, different parties can even use
82 the same piece of evidence in support of their opposing narratives. Conservation science is not
83 neutral in this regard either. It has an inherently subjective component; it has a desired (more
84 biodiversity) and an undesired (less biodiversity) outcome. The different and often conflicting
85 interests of different stakeholders partly explain the wide range of narratives about
86 conservation and farming that are currently used (see Box 1) [27]. Understanding this complex
87 communication arena is important as ignoring or incorrectly connecting to existing narratives
88 may counteract the societal impact scientists aim to achieve.

89 For a scientist, science communication is rarely a full-time job. Therefore, we generally
90 lack a clear consideration of how our results can best be linked to the world-views and
91 perceptions of the people we try to reach [28]. In contrast, many stakeholders in the farming
92 arena use and develop their own narratives often with the help of communication professionals
93 to safeguard their interests, for example, economic profits. While it is important that scientists
94 listen to stakeholders from the farming sector and engage in knowledge co-production and co-
95 dissemination of the results [29], we should nevertheless develop our own independent
96 communication strategies. This does not imply ignoring other stakeholders, but rather involves
97 clear positioning of the implications of scientific studies within the context provided by other
98 stakeholders, pursuing accuracy and plausibility. By doing so, the evidence from scientific
99 studies will stand a better chance of being heard by the targeted stakeholders amidst the many

100 competing narratives with different levels of support and value presented by different
101 stakeholders.

102 To help scientists working on biodiversity-friendly farming navigate the complexities
103 of impactful communication in a research field characterized by societally conflicting interests,
104 we first identify the currently prevailing biodiversity conservation and farming narratives. We
105 then propose the term “biodiversity” as a **boundary concept** that can facilitate starting
106 dialogues among stakeholders with contrasting interests. Finally, we demonstrate how
107 scientists can develop their own narratives to enhance effective communication.

108 **Glossary:**

109 **Biodiversity-friendly farming:** any type of agriculture that specifically aims to
110 maintain or promote biodiversity.

111 **Boundary concept:** a loose and flexible concept used in different social realities that
112 represents a common reference point, allowing stakeholders with different backgrounds to
113 communicate and collaborate, creating shared goals.

114 **Corporate farming:** types of agriculture conducted by multinational corporations or
115 companies, where site managers and farm workers rather than farmers carry out agricultural
116 practices.

117 **Effective communication:** the process of transmitting information, ideas, opinions, and
118 knowledge, in a way that enhances listening, understanding, and the taking of action and that
119 results in messages being received with clarity and purpose.

120 **High-input farming systems:** any type of agriculture that is being based primarily on
121 external inputs such as fuel, fertilisers, and pesticides.

122 **Narratives:** communication tools that explain events in a logical way and that define
123 and position actors, set the context and devise the framework to delineate objectives, and
124 prescribe action.

125 **Science communication:** wide range of communication activities that connect science
126 and society. Common goals of science communication include informing non-experts about
127 scientific findings, raising public awareness of and interest in the topic under study, influencing
128 people's behaviours, informing public policy, and engaging with diverse communities to
129 address societal problems.

130 **Navigating the biodiversity conservation and farming narratives.**

131 How to promote conservation while maintaining yields represents a so-called “wicked
132 problem” that does not have a single, straight-forward solution and that has consequences that
133 go beyond the environmental dimension [30]. How to best conserve biodiversity is open to
134 interpretation and debate and strongly depends on a person’s occupation and worldview. As a
135 result of social and cultural processes and conflicts, conservation discourses have evolved in
136 different parts of the world and through the decades from “nature for itself”, “nature despite
137 people”, to “nature for people”, and recently “nature and people” [31]. Thus, many narratives
138 with their own arguments have been developed (see Fig. 1 for a conceptual summary). Here
139 we discuss some of the most common ones in the farming-conservation debate.

140 *Anthropocentric narratives* are currently widely being used to argue for biodiversity
141 conservation. They fundamentally state that safeguarding biodiversity is important because it
142 provides essential services to mankind. According to this narrative, biodiversity should be
143 considered an essential factor supporting agricultural production [32,33]. However, most
144 farmers, and especially those implementing **high-input farming**, do not perceive any

145 economic benefits from biodiversity because private ecosystem service benefits are often
146 outweighed by the costs of enhancing biodiversity [34,35]. Enhancing biodiversity on farms
147 does generally promote public goods like wildlife conservation or landscape aesthetics.
148 However, economic considerations often take precedence among the criteria farmers use to
149 make decisions. As a result, the anthropocentric narrative is not very convincing to most
150 farmers. Using it may even signal to farmers a lack of understanding of real-world farming
151 complexities, mainly determined by the *economic narrative* [36].

152 Especially in areas where conservation conflicts have emerged, like Eastern Africa,
153 Western Amazonia, or the Southeast Asian Archipelago [37], questions are being raised for
154 whom and for what to conserve [38,39]. Alternative narratives have been developed
155 emphasising topics such as governance quality, equity or the extension of rights for non-human
156 entities and future generations. These subjects, mostly elaborated in developing countries [40–
157 42], reinforce the morality of care and the interdependency with nature, as advocated by
158 indigenous people and local communities [43,44], contributing to *spiritual and identity*
159 *narratives* [45,46]. Despite some of these narratives now being adopted by scientists and
160 societal stakeholders in western countries [47], they still do not play a major role there [48].
161 The debate on which narrative for biodiversity conservation is most valid, powerful or
162 convincing is ongoing [49,50].

163 Farming discourses have also evolved through time and the demands for action have
164 broadened [7] from “closing the yield gap” –still a widely used argument in regions such as
165 Sub-Saharan Africa or South Asia–, towards “diet quality and adequacy” –a common narrative
166 in Southeast Asia or the Caribbean region–, “social justice” –commonly used by Via
167 Campesina movement [51]– and “environmental sustainability” –lively debated among
168 European and North American policymakers. However, the dominant *agroeconomic narrative*

169 usually deploys arguments such as food security framed under capitalistic conceptions
170 disseminated by high-input and **corporate farming** stakeholders [52,53]. These types of
171 farming are spreading steadily not only in western countries, but much more rapidly in large
172 areas of Asia, Latin America and Africa [54–57].

173 Based on the western intellectual tradition [53], the *agroeconomic narrative* considers
174 nature ruled by “mechanistic relationships” and frames farming under the ideas of “progress
175 and control” [58]. According to this paradigm, integrating biodiversity conservation in
176 mainstream farming is primarily dependent on economic incentives (e.g. higher prices for
177 wildlife-friendly products) and regulatory instruments (e.g. higher taxes on unsustainable
178 inputs, prescribing farming practices) [12]. Examples that support this paradigm include the
179 set-aside regulation that had significant positive effects on farmland biodiversity although it
180 had been designed to reduce excess food production [59]. This worldview did not initially
181 consider the ecosystem processes, functions, and services that are regulated by biodiversity.
182 Proponents of *ecological intensification* of agriculture [33,60], upgraded this viewpoint by
183 leveraging ecosystem services to sustain agricultural production and reducing its
184 environmental footprint by relying more on ecological processes. Nevertheless, ecological
185 intensification does not challenge the economic rationale of industrial farming such as market
186 prices or lowering production cost. Thus, this approach has been criticised by some proponents
187 of agroecology, since it does not necessarily lead to more self-sufficient agricultural systems
188 [61].

189 Agroecology was firstly defined as the application of ecological principles to
190 agricultural systems and practices, or the science providing the evidence base for this.
191 However, this definition has evolved through time, and its definition varies depending on the
192 context [62]. For example, agroecology can be considered to be mainly a scientific discipline

193 (e.g. in Germany), mainly an agricultural practice that applies ecological principles (e.g. in
194 France) or mainly a political and social movement (e.g. in Brazil, India, or Senegal) [63]. Some
195 forms of agroecology embrace more holistic perspectives, often framed under “healing” and
196 “health” metaphors [58] and focusing on smallholding farming. Agroecology and similar
197 concepts like *regenerative farming* or conservation agriculture are gaining popularity and
198 importance in food systems debates. Often in *agroecology narratives*, social justice discourses
199 and food system sustainability are dominant and biodiversity conservation is not the main
200 consideration.

201 In sum, both biodiversity conservation and farming are conceived differently by
202 different parties. Biodiversity conservation narratives are not only used to counteract farming
203 narratives but also other conservation narratives and vice versa. Thus, a myriad of discourses
204 and counter-discourses are continuously elaborated to enhance or conceal conflicting causes
205 and articulate convincing frameworks. This can lead to rhetoric like equalling environmental
206 sustainability to social justice in the Sustainable Development Agenda [64]. This, in turn, can
207 result in the oversimplification of problems, creating potential misunderstandings and
208 polarization between stakeholders, and promoting dissensions on how to approach
209 sustainability [65].

210 **Box 1: Key narratives of different stakeholders in the biodiversity conservation-farming**
211 **arena.**

212 To illustrate how different stakeholders position themselves along the narratives continuum we
213 use Europe as an example because biodiversity conservation in farmland is a topic of extensive
214 debate in science as well as society. We have analysed a total of 5988 digital press releases and
215 news texts covering the period of 2015-2020 from the webpages of 40 farming related
216 European organisations that have recognition for representing stakeholders in decision-making.

217 We have looked at their positioning based on their use of selected keywords using text mining
218 and multivariate analysis (see supplementary material for more detail).

219 Our results show that environmental non-governmental organizations (NGOs), the industry
220 sector and advocacy groups use narratives that are predominantly characterized by distinct
221 keywords (Fig. I-A). “Nature”, “wildlife” and “restore”, are used commonly in press releases
222 and news items of NGOs, aligned with conservationist terminology. Stakeholders from the
223 industry sector often mention “market” and “productivity” in their communication lining up
224 with productivism vocabulary, and advocacy groups can be distinguished by writing about
225 “conventional”, “organic” and “soil”, reflecting on agronomic topics. With respect to word use
226 in their communications, farmer organizations are located firmly in the middle. Their use of
227 keywords shows considerable overlap with industry and advocacy groups, in contrast, there is
228 no overlap with the terminology used by NGOs and scientific advice —however only one
229 organization was considered in the latter—, that commonly employ topics from sustainable
230 development framework.

231 In a second analysis we focused on press releases and news items that did contain the keyword
232 biodiversity and analysed which other keywords were most frequently co-occurring (Fig. I-B).
233 This shows that when farmers organizations do communicate about biodiversity, they seem to
234 place it most frequently in a functional context (“benefitting”, “soil”, “quality”,
235 “safeguarding”). Conservation NGOs almost show an opposite pattern, with biodiversity most
236 frequently being mentioned together with “protect”, “society” and “development”. Industry
237 sector is closer to economic narratives talking about “market”, “management” and “functions”
238 when referring to biodiversity, whereas in advocacy groups the biodiversity usage seems
239 relatively scarce. Intergovernmental agencies show a steadier cooccurrence of these keywords
240 with the term biodiversity, but “development” and “protect” detach.

241 A deeper analysis of how the biodiversity-aligned terms influence behaviour could provide
242 useful insights into how to frame messages to reach different audiences [66].

243 **Using biodiversity as a compatible boundary concept.**

244 In line with a recent study [67], Fig. I-B suggests that the perception of what
245 biodiversity entails varies widely between different stakeholder groups. Scientists generally
246 refer to the formal definition of biodiversity linked to processes, goods, and values [68].
247 However, both NGOs and scientists often equate biodiversity to nature and wildlife. Contrary,
248 farmers generally have a more functional notion [69]. They often equate biodiversity with
249 species groups that functionally contribute to agriculture like pollinators, natural enemies, or
250 soil biota, but also harmful organisms like pests and plagues. Yet other stakeholder groups
251 perceive biodiversity related to aesthetics or sense of place [67,69]. Importantly, while
252 biodiversity has different connotations and values for different stakeholders [70] that often
253 have opposing narratives, all connotations are primarily positive. This may be explained by the
254 fact that biodiversity does not yet symbolize a specific worldview and its image remains mostly
255 neutral in controversial issues [69]. For instance, farming stakeholders are regularly using the
256 word biodiversity in their online communication independently of their narrative and in
257 connection to constructive ideas (see Box 2). This suggests that biodiversity could be used as
258 a compatible boundary concept because different stakeholders associate with it in positive,
259 albeit different, ways and could therefore get stakeholders together, help to share information
260 seamlessly, and to cooperate effectively to find solutions for potentially controversial
261 conservation problems. However, while biodiversity could be a great starting point, it also has
262 been known to occasionally lead to conflict in the when different stakeholders place value on
263 contrasting biodiversity components that require different management strategies. Hence, as

264 the conversation evolves, these different views of biodiversity should be explored jointly to
265 prevent tensions and conflict in the long term.

266 **Box 2: The use of the term biodiversity by different stakeholders in the European**
267 **farming-biodiversity conservation playing field.**

268 Out of the 4955 analysed press releases and news items from advocacy groups, farmer
269 organizations, agri-industry sector, intergovernmental agencies and NGO's, a total of 1737
270 (35%) included the term biodiversity. As expected, farmer organizations and especially
271 stakeholders from agri-industry sector use the biodiversity term less than intergovernmental
272 agencies, NGOs, and advocacy groups (Fig. II-A). When these stakeholders talk about
273 biodiversity and farming, each group highlights different aspects (Fig. II-B-F).
274 Intergovernmental agencies, NGOs and advocacy groups communicate fairly similar and
275 mainly centre on the science policy interface, focusing on aspects such as "European Union"
276 or biodiversity "loss". In contrast, the science policy interface does not feature much in the
277 communications of farmers organizations and agri-industry sector although both communicate
278 about the "farm to fork strategy". Farmers frequently focus on actions mentioning specific
279 measures such as flower "strips" and "lines". It is notable that the agri-industry sector is the
280 only group that communicates about "pressure", "ambitions, and "challenges" in relation to
281 biodiversity and farming.

282 Based on this example, it is probably not a good idea to open a dialogue about biodiversity-
283 friendly farming with a farmer choosing technical topics far from their direct interests such as
284 ecosystem services or climate regulations, which would be better suited for creating
285 understanding and trust with NGOs and intergovernmental agencies. When opening a
286 conversation process with a farmer, scientists can best start focusing on specific aspects that

287 farmers experience on a daily basis such as yield, soil quality, or how to safeguard the farm for
288 his/her children to foster comprehension of ideas and perspectives.

289 **Why scientists need to develop their own narrative.**

290 Narratives as efficient communication tools can enhance understanding and improve
291 memory retention [71]. By using clear narratives built around their study outcomes, scientists
292 can engage to a larger proportion of a target audience than by just presenting facts and figures
293 [24]. Furthermore, scientists should be aware that if they do not frame the outcome of their
294 work, others will do it. In other words, when scientists fail to communicate and position the
295 implications of their results, stakeholders are free to use these in ways that best serve their own
296 interests. This means scientists need to become a stakeholder in the discussion and take a stand.
297 Depending on a scientist's preference, taking a stand can range from formulating the
298 implications and societal relevance of scientific studies in a language that laypeople can
299 understand to becoming an advocate for the cause.

300 Not all scientists are comfortable with taking a position in debates, but in the
301 biodiversity conservation and farming arena, not taking a stand is inevitably also taking a stand.
302 Just one you have no control over. Furthermore, most scientific methods and study designs are
303 consciously or unconsciously coloured by the assumptions we make, the frameworks on which
304 we base our questions, the hypotheses we choose to test. Particularly for science addressing
305 societally relevant topics, one could therefore argue that neutral science does not exist.
306 Importantly, taking a stand does not have to compromise the integrity of scientists; it only
307 means that we explicitly voice our view of the world. We can achieve this by always clearly
308 distinguishing between the evidence produced by science and what we think this means for
309 society (i.e. the interpretations, implications and framing) when communicating. Besides, there
310 are transparent and robust processes to mitigate the risk of mistrust, for example by clearly

311 acknowledging the assumptions, uncertainty, and caveats of our messages [72]. Critical
312 thinking will be always fundamental, as well as applying intellectual standards such as
313 accuracy, fairness, and transparency.

314 Finally, if the goal is maximizing societal impact to contribute to biodiversity
315 conservation on farmland, scientists cannot work in isolation. We, as scientists, need to listen
316 first and embrace the value of a pluralistic approach, where drawing on different ways of
317 knowing and doing can help find creative solutions [29]. It is pivotal to connect with different
318 stakeholders, acknowledge their needs, and translate results into strategic narratives. The
319 narrative of conservation scientists should balance between following scientific evidence,
320 finding an equilibrium between persuasion and accuracy and being inclusive —i.e., recognising
321 and inviting potential conflicting positions. Being inclusive may help build trust relationships
322 that can ultimately result in a larger societal impact [73]. Nevertheless, scientists should be
323 aware when their involvement in multi-stakeholder initiatives merely represents greenwashing
324 by other stakeholders [74].

325 **Building an impactful narrative based on scientific evidence.**

326 Many narratives for biodiversity-friendly farming that are popular among policymakers
327 and scientists focus on win-win scenarios [10,75]. These narratives generally do not
328 acknowledge the many trade-offs that occur when aiming to conserve biodiversity on farmland
329 [76]. Recent evidence indicates win-win scenarios are rare and generally biodiversity
330 conservation and crop yield or farm profit trade off against each other [35,77]. To a farmer this
331 may be obvious; for instance, land taken out of production to grow wildflowers cannot be used
332 to produce crops and, although under specific conditions enhanced pollination or pest control
333 might compensate for yield loss [78], this is generally not the case [79]. Fairly presenting the
334 advantages and disadvantages of biodiversity-friendly farming might be difficult to

335 communicate in the short term but might be pivotal in the long-term. Additionally, the
336 importance of emotions and values, rather than merely facts, is often underestimated by
337 scientists [24]. Studies have shown that, when taking decisions, practitioners often rely more
338 on intuition or opinion than on scientific evidence [80]. Scientists can improve the impact of
339 their narratives by acknowledging and using these insights for example by letting farmers do
340 part of the communication.

341 Once the key message for a narrative has been chosen, scientists should carefully consider how
342 to deliver their message. Each narrative should be tailored to the evidence scientists want to
343 communicate, the key societal implications that the scientist thinks it entails and the targeted
344 audience. While there are no cookbooks on how to do this, effective narratives need to address
345 three key questions, presented in a specific order and in a way that appeals to their audience
346 [81]: “why”, “what” and “how” (Box 3). Scientists should take the time to come up with clear
347 answers to these three questions and rehearse how to articulate them before engaging with
348 different stakeholders.

349 **Box 3: Developing an impactful scientific narrative: an example.**

350 Effective narratives require a message that is concise but comprehensive [82]. The exact
351 content and terminology might differ for different audiences or in different contexts (e.g. for
352 different taxa) but an example of an effective strategy to get across your message is to follow
353 the formula Why-What-How.

354 1- **Start with “Why”**. A clear “why” helps to define your core beliefs and transmit a sense
355 of mission [81]. This enhances trust since your audience understands why you are advocating
356 for a given idea, and what is your agenda. As shown in the main text, the term biodiversity
357 functions as a boundary concept and hence it can be used to connect with a wide range of

358 people. Since the reasons why we should conserve biodiversity on farmland are complex, it is
359 often helpful to use metaphors: for example, concepts such as complementarity can be
360 expressed comparing biodiversity with a tractor, which requires from all the gears (species) to
361 work properly, redundancy can be explained as a football team —or any other team sport—,
362 where only a limited number of players are on the playing field at any point in time, but we
363 need a large and diverse group of teammates (species) on the substitutes' bench as a backup,
364 and interconnectedness or interdependence can be compared to a tapestry, where the interlacing
365 threads can be compared to the links between species, environment and humans[83]. It may be
366 necessary to employ different analogies in order to convince different stakeholders in a given
367 narrative.

368 **2- Continue with “What”.** The ‘what’ presents your key take-home message. Ideally, it
369 should be one short, and direct sentence that presents in clear and non-technical terms your
370 take-home message. Best messages are balanced and honest, and not empty slogans.
371 Rehearsing a couple of key messages targeting different audiences helps being precise,
372 consistent, and earnest.

373 **Finalize with “How”.** Explain how to achieve the “what”. This is particularly important
374 for farmers but is not something scientists excel at. The “how” should be concrete and can best
375 be transmitted by success stories that are real and close to the audience's hearts [84]. Success
376 stories can range from conservation [85] to farmers income [78] and farm health stories[86].

377 Note that we do not suggest which should be your why what and how. The answer to this
378 should emerge from listening to the relevant stakeholders, integrating the available scientific
379 evidence and critically evaluating all this information on the light of the prevailing narratives.

380

381 **Concluding Remarks**

382 The challenge of how to integrate biodiversity management into farming practices needs
383 effective scientific communication to ensure uptake by farmers and other stakeholders (see
384 Outstanding questions). Many narratives regarding biodiversity-friendly farming are already
385 being used in the public arena. Researchers should acknowledge these and strategically position
386 their own narratives to maximize impact, becoming a legitimate stakeholder in the
387 conversation. The use of biodiversity as a boundary concept that can bring together contrasting
388 stakeholders, and the use of narratives that clearly explain the why, the what and the how can
389 help bridge the gap between science and practice.

390 Outstanding Questions:

391 Who is communicating with farmers about biodiversity, why, and what narratives are being used in
392 different parts of the world?

393 Which messages are reinforced, and which are hidden by the narratives of the key stakeholders in the
394 farmland biodiversity conservation playing field?

395 How does the variety of practitioners involved in farming activities –farmers, farm workers, managers,
396 etc.– respond to dominant narratives in the different countries and cultures?

397 Which narratives are the most likely to lead to action in favour to biodiversity friendly farming?

398 What are the most effective tools and channels to communicate about biodiversity- friendly farming
399 and how does this differ between key stakeholders?

400

401

402

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598 Figures with captions:

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601 **Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the biodiversity conservation and farming narratives.** Different
 602 conservation narratives are presented in bubbles. Fundamental ideas behind each conservation narrative are
 603 underlined. Arrows indicate common associated terms and arguments of each narrative. Farming discourses
 604 encompassing agriculture dimensions are presented with quotation marks. Green depicts biodiversity conservation
 605 and orange depicts farming storylines (see legend).

606 **Figure I: Stakeholder positioning in the communication environment.**

608 A) NMDS ordination based on word frequency of selected keywords (grey dots; only some keywords are named
 609 to allow legibility). Each polygon represents a different Stakeholder type (see legend). Coloured dots locate each

610 studied organization for each stakeholder type. NMDS1 axis displays a gradient from agronomic to sustainable
 611 development terms whereas the NMDS2 axis exhibit a gradient from production towards conservationist topics.
 612 B) Chart representing per stakeholder type the probability of keywords co-occurring with the term ‘biodiversity’
 613 more often than expected. Data was derived from 363 digital press releases and news texts that contained the term
 614 biodiversity at least five times. The number of times the term “biodiversity” used was: Farmer Organizations 128
 615 times in 13 texts; Industry Sector 165 times in 13 texts; Intergovernmental Agencies 1558 times in 139 texts;
 616 Advocacy Groups 899 times in 67 texts; and NGOs 1348 times in 131 texts (see supplementary materials for more
 617 details).

618
 619 **Figure II: Biodiversity term usage by stakeholder type.**

620 Proportion of texts including the terms biodiversity & farming (yellow), only biodiversity (green) and without
 621 including any of these terms by stakeholder type in the studied corpus.

622

623 **Figure III: Top 20 biodiversity correlated topics used by stakeholders.**

624 Data was derived from 214 digital press releases and news containing both terms: farming at least one time and
 625 the biodiversity at least five times. The analysis context was narrowed to the sentence frame. Sample size varies
 626 according to stakeholder type: The number of times the term “biodiversity” used was: Farmer Organizations 122
 627 times in 12 texts; Industry Sector 165 times in 13 texts; Intergovernmental Agencies 846 times in 68 texts;
 628 Advocacy Groups 846 times in 41 texts; and NGOs 875 times in 80 texts. Size of the bars is proportional to their
 629 relative probability of occurrence together with the term biodiversity.

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